

Effect of the Perceived Functionality of Non-Prototypical Product on Emotional Appraisal

Eunkyeung, Park* Woo-Hun, Lee ** Myung-Suk, Kim***

* Daejeon, South Korea, tubitu@kaist.ac.kr

** Daejeon, South Korea, woohun.lee@kaist.ac.kr

*** Daejeon, South Korea, mskim@kaist.ac.kr

Abstract: This study was conducted as a part of ‘The study on the relationship of prototypicality of the product and customer adaption’. The aim of this study is to research on the effect of perceived functionality on emotional appraisal for different range of prototype concentration in the product category. First through literature review, the definition of prototype and the determinants of prototypicality had been studied. The research has been structured to find the range of prototype concentration in each product category through drawing a prototypical shape. Next, to study the effect of perceived functionality on the emotional appraisal, the change in emotional appraisal on novelty, familiarity, reliability, and preference when image of non-prototypical products from each product category was shown without and with functional description was analyzed. In this study, products are sorted into two types according to the range of prototype concentration. In each type, the certain patterns of change in emotional appraisal were shown when the function of the non-prototypical product was perceived. This study shows the implications for different effects of functional perception on emotional appraisal in non-prototypical products depending on the range of prototype concentration in the product category

Key words: Prototype, Prototypicality, Perceived Functionality, Categorization, Emotional Appraisal

1. Introduction

Categorization, which is the process of building a particular concept of the perceived object to recognize, differentiate and understand it, is a fundamental activity of humankind. Humans have been categorizing every environmental factors based on the specific criteria, perceiving objects as a meaningful unit rather than as an individual object, being able to understand the situation of their surroundings quickly and accurately.

But as humankind had started to use tools to improve the living conditions, the objects of categorization had expanded from the nature to daily necessities. Since the industrial revolution, products with many different uses have been mass-produced, and product categorization has become an important issue for creating new products. And the concept, which consumers have for the particular product category, is a prototype of the product [1].

The effects of the prototype, or the effects of similarities between the prototypes in existing product categories and a new product in the same categories, have been studied in many ways [2, 3]. But the past studies show limitations as they have not considered the effect of range of prototype concentration in the product category on the emotional appraisal.

Present study compares the change on the emotional appraisal of the non-prototypical product according to the perception of functionality in the daily life product as the range of prototype concentration in each product category.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Prototype Theory

Categorization is the process of grouping objects based on their similar properties to perceive them quickly and accurately [4]. It can be viewed as the process of comparison of similarity between the new objects and the basic concepts of the objects. Based on the approach, Eleanor Rosch proposed prototype theory [5]. In short, there exists the central representation of a category; it has the most common features of members of that category. Thus, a concept of category is distributed around this best example, and prototypicality is the degree to which an object is representative of a category [6]. In addition to, prototypical instances of category are more likely than non-prototypical instances to be named sooner in free recall of category instances [7, 8], classified more quickly, learned more rapidly as category members [9].

2.2. Determinant of Prototypicality

Loken categorized the factors of prototypicality into three major determinants in his study [10, 11, 12]. First determinant is the attribute sharing, or the amount of common attribute in the product categories. There are two major approaches, family resembles [13] and feature-similarity [14]. Family resemble is the degree of commonness of features of a product with other members in the product category, while feature-similarity considers not only common features but also difference between the features. That is, the more prototypical product has the more common features and less different features with other members in the category. Second determinant is the frequency of exposure of the product. In other words, from a particular product category, products that are more frequently exposed become more familiar, and perceived as the prototype of the category. Third determinant is the goal-derived or goal-relevant attitude of a product. Barsalou [15, 16] suggested goal-derived categories that prototypical members have not similar attribute but have more value for fulfilling a goal. In summary, the determinants of prototypicality are the amount of common attribute, frequency of exposure and the degree of goal-derived attributes. Previous studies of each determinant of prototypicality and emotional appraisal show that, the amount of common attribute has inverted U-shape relationship with preference [17]; repeated exposure is intrinsically pleasant by making cognitive processing fluent [18], but the effect is depending on the stimuli [19] and the over-exposure can lead boredom [20]. Goal-derived attribute has proportional relation with preference [21].

3. Research Objective

Despite of the degree of goal-derived attributes of a product is related to its prototypicality [22, 23, 24] generally, a physically dissimilar product with high goal-derived attributes is not easily perceived as a prototype of the product category [25]. In addition, the prototype may not be always same to everyone; moreover it may be more than one in some product categories [26].

Therefore, in the present study, a prototype is defined as the physically best example in the category. And a non-prototypical product is defined as the product which does not have prototypical features, but may have goal-derived attributes, or functionality.

The objective of this study is to examine the effect of perceived functionality on emotional appraisal with non-prototypical product in the product categories which are classified by the range of prototype concentration. Thus the following hypotheses are proposed.

H1. Frequency of exposure of product category will have effect on the range of prototype concentration.

H2. Effect of perceived functionality for non-prototypical product on emotional appraisal will be different for different range of prototype concentration.

H2-1. Increase in novelty will be higher for narrow range of prototype concentration than for wide range of prototype concentration.

H2-2. Increase in familiarity will be lower for narrow range of prototype concentration than for wide range of prototype concentration.

H2-3. Increase in reliability will be lower for narrow range of prototype concentration than for wide range of prototype concentration.

H2-4. Increase in preference will be lower for narrow range of prototype concentration than for wide range of prototype concentration.

3. Research Methodology

In this study, to classify the product for daily use as 2 types according to the range of prototype concentration, prototypical shape drawing experiment was executed. And for each type, to see the change in effect of perceived functionality on emotional appraisal, emotional appraisal experiment was conducted.

3.1. Prototypical Shape Drawing Experiment

In the prototypical shape drawing experiment, to find the range of prototype concentration of product categories, people were told to draw the prototypical shape for each product category. First, 10 product categories in daily life products [27], which have few functions that people can easily recognize, were selected. Next, experiment sheets with names of each product category were given to 11 students of industrial design majors to draw the prototypical shape of each product category and to evaluate the encounter frequency of the each product category in the 5 point scale.

Draw a prototypical(typical) figure that represent the product category.

1. Steam humidifier	2. Post-it	3. Mouse pad	4. Keyboard dust brush	5. USB Memory card
Exposure rate Row ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ High	Exposure rate Row ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ High	Exposure rate Row ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ High	Exposure rate Row ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ High	Exposure rate Row ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ High
6. Pen with cap	7. Door stopper	8. Hanger attached wall	9. Cork of bottle	10. Holder of Tee bag
Exposure rate Row ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ High	Exposure rate Row ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ High	Exposure rate Row ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ High	Exposure rate Row ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ High	Exposure rate Row ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ High

Figure.1 Experiment sheet for prototypical shape drawing

3.2. Emotional Appraisal Experiment

To study the effect of perceived functionality on the emotional appraisal in the 10 product category that were selected in the prototypical shape drawing experiments, 10 non-prototypical products in the market that have low amount of common attributes are selected. 20 students (8 male, 12 female) of industrial design major participated in the experiment and was done in 2 sessions.

In the first session, only the full-screen images of the 10 products were shown in a power point presentation, and the questionnaire to make emotional appraisal for each product was given. After looking at each product image, possibility of predicting the function to and the 7 point scale evaluation of novelty, familiarity, reliability, and preference is to be conducted.

Figure.2 Product images shown by power point slides

Please answer the following questions after looking at the image slides.

1. Can you predict the function of this product? Yes No

2. Please give a rating of 1 to 7 for the following evaluation of the product.

Novelty

Low 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 High

Familiarity

Low 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 High

Reliability

Low 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 High

Preference

Low 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 High

Figure.3 Questionnaire for the emotional appraisal of each product

In the second session, previous 10 product images were shown with text description of the function through the power point presentation, and questionnaire to make emotional appraisal for each product was given. The question asks if the prediction made in session 1 was correct, and the 7 point scale evaluation of novelty, familiarity, reliability, and preference.

Figure.4 Product images shown by power point slides with explanations

1. If answered predictable for the previous question, was the prediction of the function correct?
 Yes No

2. Please give a rating of 1 to 7 for the following evaluation of the product.

Novelty

Low 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 High

Familiarity

Low 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 High

Reliability

Low 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 High

Preference

Low 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 High

Figure.5 Questionnaire for the emotional appraisal of each product after functional description

4. Results

4.1. Two Types of Product as the Range of Prototype Concentration

Prototypical shape drawing experiment resulted in categorizing product category into narrow range of prototype concentration and wide range of prototype concentration by their range of prototype concentration. Results for prototypical shape drawing for each product categories are as following.

Table 1. Type 1: Product categories with narrow range of prototype concentration

Product Category	Average of Exposure rate	Prototypical Shape	Identical / Total drawing
Post-it	4.91		11/11
Mouse pad	4.64		10/11
USB Memory card	4.82		11/11
Pen with cap	4.64		10/11
Door stopper	3.27		9/11

Table 2. Type 2: Product categories with wide range of prototype concentration

Product Category	Average of Exposure rate	Prototypical Shape (more than two)		Non-prototype (Non-typical shape)
Steam humidifier	3.55			
Keyboard Dust brush	2.09			
Hanger attached wall	3.27			
Cork of bottle	2.64			
Holder of Tea bag	1.6			

By comparing Type 1 and Type 2 product categories shown in table 1 and table 2, product categories with narrow range of prototype concentration have relatively higher exposure rate in daily life than that of product categories with wide range. But in the case of door stopper in Type 1, 9 out of 11 drew the same prototypical shape, thus showing average exposure frequency of 3.29, which is relatively low for a narrow range of prototype concentration. Also steam humidifier and hanger attached wall in Type 2, shows average of exposure frequency of 3.55 and 3.27, which is high for a wide range of prototype concentration. Therefore H1 hypothesis, frequency of exposure of product category will have effect on the range of prototype concentration, has been partially verified, existence of additional independent factor is assumed.

4.2. Comparison of Emotional Appraisal Before and After Perceiving Functionality

To verify the hypotheses, we used SPSS's paired t-test to compare the change on emotional appraisal according to the perception of functionality of non-prototypical products in type 1 and type 2

Figure.6 Graph of showing change in emotional appraisal for non-prototypical product in Type 1

From the above graph, paired t-test shows that the difference between conditions (before functional explanation and after functional explanation) is significant for novelty ($t=-3.058$, $df=94$, $p=0.003$), familiarity ($t=-3.192$, $df=94$, $p=0.002$), and reliability ($t=-3.136$, $df=94$, $p=0.002$). But paired t-test also shows that the difference between conditions of preference not to be significant ($t=-.203$, $df=94$, $p=0.840$). That is, perceived functionality increases novelty, familiarity, and reliability appraisal for narrow range of prototype concentration (type 1) products, but does not effect preference.

Figure.7 Graph of showing change in emotional appraisal for non-prototypical product in Type 2

From the above graph, paired t-test shows that the difference between conditions is significant for novelty($t=-3.827$, $df=86$, $p<0.00025$), familiarity($t=-3.325$, $df=86$, $p=0.001$), and reliability($t=4.119$, $df=86$, $p<0.00025$). And paired t-test also shows that the difference between conditions of preference is significant ($t=-2.248$, $df=86$, $p=0.027$). That is, perceived functionality increased novelty, familiarity, reliability, and preference appraisal significantly for wide of prototype concentration (type 2) products.

Figure.8 Graph of showing comparison of increasing amount of emotional appraisal in Type1 and Type2

To clarify, regardless of prototypicality range, novelty, familiarity, and reliability shows tendency to increase with function perception, and for narrow prototypicality range, no meaningful preference changes were seen, but for wide prototypicality range, functional perception caused tendency to increase in preference.

4.3. The Effect of Frequency of Exposure and the Range of Prototype Concentration on the Change of Emotional Appraisal

Experiment.1 shows that the frequency of product category's exposure has partial effect on the range of prototype concentration. Therefore, three-way MANOVA test is conducted to examine the change of emotional appraisal for different frequency exposures and range of prototype concentration, which is used to classify the two types.

Table 3. Result of a significant three-way multivariate interaction

Exposure Frequency	Type 1			Type 2		
	High (4.91)	Middle (4.70)	Low (3.27)	High (3.55)	Middle (2.67)	Low (1.6)
	Post-it	USB memory card / Mouse pad / Pen with cap	Door stopper	Steam humidifier	Hanger / Cork of bottle / Keyboard dust brush	Holder of tea bag
Change of Novelty	0.778*	0.474*	1.053*	-0.500	1.000***	0.800*
Change of Familiarity	0.556	0.579**	-0.105	0.250	0.569***	0.450
Changes of Reliability	1.333**	0.298	0.421	0.312	0.804***	0.450
Change of Preference	1.167*	-0.316	-0.053	-0.750*	0.588***	0.650

* $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.025$, *** $p<0.005$

First, for each type, product with the highest exposure frequency and lowest exposure frequency is chosen and categorized. Excluding these selected products, three other products are categorized as middle exposure frequency. After that, paired-t test is conducted to the products with high, middle, and low exposure frequency. The test results indicate that perceived functionality for type 1 products of middle exposure frequency significantly increases novelty and familiarity, but has no meaningful effect on preference. In the case of high exposure frequency, perceived functionality influences the novelty, reliability and preference positively. And when the exposure frequency is low, only novelty showed meaningful increase. For type 2 products, when exposure rate is middle, novelty, familiarity, reliability, and preference all showed meaningful increase. In case of low exposure rate, all emotional appraisals increased but only novelty showed meaningful amount of change. And when the exposure frequency is high, preference showed meaningful decrease.

5. Discussion

5.1. Conclusions

This study is to examine the effect of functional perception on change in emotional appraisal- novelty, familiarity, reliability and preference- for different range of prototype concentration of each product category. In order to do so, first, prototypical shape drawing experiment was done to find the range of prototype concentration in each product category. Next, product categories were classified into type 1 and type 2 by their range of prototype concentration. And to find the effect of functional perception on emotional appraisal, comparison of emotional appraisal- novelty, familiarity, reliability and preference- for non-prototypical products before and after perceiving function was done. Finally, because the frequency of exposure and the range of prototype concentration did not show any meaningful relationship in some product categories, effect on emotional appraisal by frequency of exposure and the range of prototype concentration was examined simultaneously. Below is the summary of the result of this study.

First, exposure frequency of product category had effect on the range of prototype concentration. Generally product categories with higher exposure frequency had narrow prototype concentration. But this is not the case for all product categories, therefore there seems to be other factors involved, possibly involvement between consumers and the product.

Second, generally, perceived functionality of non-prototypical product caused meaningful increase in novelty, familiarity, and reliability appraisal regardless of the types. But preference increased only in the product categories with wide range of prototype concentration. It has implication for non-prototypical products, when people have no convinced prototype there is a better chance to have their preference increased, compare to when people have a single product prototype of those product categories.

Third, for product categories with narrow range of prototype concentration, perceived functionality of non-prototypical product did not show any meaningful relationship with other emotional appraisal, but caused significant increase in novelty.

Finally, for product categories with wide range of prototype concentration, perceived functionality of non-prototypical product had positive effect on emotional appraisal, but for wide range of prototype concentration with high exposure frequency, non-prototypical product's perceived functionality had significantly negative effect on preference change. Therefore, when designing non-prototypical products in product categories with wide range of prototype concentration, it is likely to derive positive emotional appraisal by functionality in the

case of low frequency of exposure are likely to derive positive emotional appraisal, but in the case of frequency of exposure is high, other factors need to be considered.

5.2. Further works

This study researched about the effect of functional perception on emotional appraisal of novelty, familiarity, reliability and preference for different range of prototype concentration in product category. But the measurement of emotional appraisal has been done progressively within-subject experiment, therefore it is seen that difference in order effect between pretest and posttest causes limitation on gaining objective data. Also, other factors besides exposure frequency, effecting product category's range of prototype concentration should be studied more. Therefore in the following research, in-depth literature review on the determinants of prototype concentration of product categories will be done. And based on the result, more studies will be done to give of guidelines to apply the implications to product design process with the intention to evoke certain emotion.

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